

ISic3548

I.Sicily inscription 3548

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Drepanum

Place of origin (modern)

Trapani

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost, Museo Pepoli (Trapani) ms. 33 and 221

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337212

1. θεοῖς πᾶσι

2. Δρεπαναί [ων]

3. πόλεω[ς] σ[ω]τήρσιν

4. [τ]ραπέ[ζ]α[ν] καὶ τ[ὸ]ν βωμὸν

5. Λ (οὔκιος) Μάλιος [— —]

6. χι[λ]ιάρχησα [ς]

7. Π Π ²⁷ρ(ropria) ρ(ecunia) or ρ(ecunia) ρ(osuit) (?) (Tybout)²⁷.

8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645623

EDCS 71000784

PHI 337212

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 52.0893

Filippi, A. 2002. Trapani: testimonianze storiche ed archeologiche. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 35: 73-87. At 73 no.9/1

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